

STUDY OF EMERGENCE OF BIOLOGICAL BALANCE ON PLANT DEVELOPMENT IN AMARANT CROPS

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Abstract. Amaranthus is a cosmopolitan genus of annual or short-lived perennial plants collectively known as amaranths. Some amaranth species are cultivated as leaf vegetables, pseudocereals, and ornamental plants. As a consequent, the article presents the investigation of the amaranth crops and their influence on plant development considering the biological balance of crops.

Keywords: amaranth, amaranth family, plants, characteristics, analysis, influence, balance.

Introduction. Plants of the amaranth family (Amaranthaceae) are annual purple or yellow-green herbaceous plants belong to the class dicotyledonous, in the order of cloves. Their height can reach 1.5 - 3.0 m [5.19-20]. When mature, the panicle reaches 30 cm long and 15 cm in diameter, and the weight of the panicle can reach up to 1 kg. Amaranth seeds are very small; the number of seeds in one panicle can reach up to 500 thousand pieces. Grain amaranth is a pseudocereal, since it has similar characteristics with cereal grains; it does not belongs to cereals. Among cereal species, the most studied are *A. cruentus* L., *A. hypochondriacus* L., *A. caudatus* L., since it is them in mainly used for food.

Amaranth belongs to light-loving plants and requires good illumination in all phases of development, exceeding the need for sorghum and corn in terms of the need for light energy [1. 147-148]. On average, the value of the assimilation coefficient of photosynthetic active radiation is 6%, and with a high agricultural background it can vary from 21 to 24% in different periods of growth and development. (pic.1).

Pic.1. The amaranth plant

Amaranth is distinguished by a high biological yield of green mass (700-800 c/ha) and seeds (25-35 c/ha). The seeds contain 16-18% protein with a high usefulness of the amino acid composition. The green mass of amaranth is well and excellently eaten by all kinds of animals. Granules, briquettes, grass flour are prepared from it, and in a mixture with green mass of corn and sunflower - a good combined silage, balanced in protein and other nutrients [2. 25-30]. This plant has antioxidant activity, which is now widely studied with the aim of introducing the constituent substances of amaranth into modern medicines for cleansing blood vessels [3. 63-64].

In the works of H.H. Elchaninova, V.G. Vasina, mixed crops of corn and amaranth turned out to be the most productive. The yield of green mass was 29.7 - 33.1 t/ha, dry - 7.0 - 7.9 t/ha. The supply of one feed unit of PP increased from 55 - 57g in single-species crops of corn to 108 - 115g in mixed crops, more - 188 - 192g - in single-species crops of amaranth. V.A. Bogomolov and V.F. Petrakova indicate that in terms of protein productivity, amaranth surpassed all crops (corn, Jerusalem artichoke, annual two- to five-component mixtures) by 2-4 times; component high-protein feed mixture [4. 357-396].

The yield of milk from the green mass of amaranth was higher than from the green mass of corn and other crops up to 2-3 and sometimes 4 times. Amaranth has been successfully used as a protein component when laying silage with low-protein crops (corn, sunflower, oats and others). In mixed sowing, it provided an increase in the protein value of silage, depending on the components, by 63 - 87%. To increase the protein nutritional value of silage when using low-protein crops to meet zootechnical requirements, one part of amaranth per 2-3 parts of the components is sufficient.

The green mass of fodder amaranth is used to obtain high-quality feed, silage, is used for the production of vitamin flour and granules. Green mass is well eaten by all household animals. Amaranth is used in feeding birds, rabbits, pigs, KRS.

When introduced into the diet of amaranth, it has a good effect on increase in livestock, increase the quantity and quality of products, contributes to cost reduction. The yield of amaranth is 3.6-6.0 t/ha of grain and up to a maximum of 180-205 t/ha of biomass. Necessary note that sowing requires a small amount of seeds, per 1 ha only 0.5-1.5 kg is required. For sowing corn, 50 kg is required, wheat - 200 kg of grain per 1 ha. Higher quality silage is obtained from the green mass of amaranth with a high protein content (60%) with the addition of corn, sorghum, sunflower, sudanese grass, mogar or cereal straw. High quality and safety of silage is achieved due to the presence in amaranth antimicrobial and volatile compounds. From phytomass amaranth is easily obtained into vitamin-herbal flour (VTM) containing protein 19-21%. The addition of amaranth significantly increases productivity of cattle, pigs, broilers.

Conclusion. In conclusion, amaranth is considered as a highly nutritious universal crop. All these qualities of amaranth, combined with high productivity, are of great interest for fodder production and contribute to the spread of this crop. Its cultivation is promising not only for fodder purposes, but also as a food, medicinal and green manure crop with a high yield of green mass. An analysis of the issue under consideration shows that, in terms of its biology and growth requirements, amaranth can be successfully cultivated in the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and be of practical interest to agricultural producers, and will also diversify production and get away from monoculture.

References:

1. Chernov, I. A. Prospects for the use of amaranth forage // New and non-traditional plants and prospects for their use. Materials II international symposium. T. 1. M. : Pushchino, 1997. S. 147-148.
2. Farniev, A.T. The role of amaranth and legumes in enriched soils nutrients / A.T. Farniev // News of Gorsky State Agrarian University №3 2012 p.25-31
3. Kononkov, P.F. Amaranth is a valuable vegetable and fodder crop multifaceted use / P.F. Kononkov, V.A. Sergeeva // Agrarian Bulletin of the Urals No. 4 (83) 2011.- P. 63-64
4. Saunders, R.M., Becker R. Amaranthus: a potential food, and feed resource / R.M. Saunders, R.S. Becker // Pomeranz Y. (ed.). Advances in cereal science and technology. – St. Paul, MN: A.A.C.C, 1984. – V. 6. – P. 357-396.
5. Zelenkov, V.N. Detection of biological activity in an in vitro model for extracts of various parts of amaranth (*Amaranthus cuneatus*) / V.N. Zelenkov, O.P. Kolesnikova, O.T. Kudaeva // Introduction of non-traditional and rare agricultural plants: mat. III Intern. sci.-prod. conf. - Penza. - 2000. - T. 1. - S. 19-

